

IRRIGATION EFFICIENCY- AN OVERVIEW

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Introduction

Irrigation efficiencies are the indices that indicate how best the water applied to the farm is being utilized. These parameters are needed to know the performance of the irrigation activity on the farm. A low value of the irrigation efficiencies, in general, implies that land, water and crops are not being managed properly. The consequence of poor irrigation efficiencies are loss of crop and wastage of nutrients and water. The major factors which affecting irrigation efficiencies are irrigation system design, quality of land preparation, selection of irrigation methods, soil texture, soil depth, land topography, stream size and skill & care of irrigator.

Fig. Factors influencing the irrigation efficiency indicator.

Definition: It is defined as the percentage of irrigation water consumed by the crop (W_c) to the water delivered to the field (W_f).

$$E_i = \frac{W_c}{W_f} \times 100$$

- It indicates how efficiently the available irrigation water is consumed by crop.
- In India irrigation efficiency with flood irrigation is around 30 to 35 %, whereas that with drip irrigation is 80 to 90 %.

Types of irrigation efficiencies

1. Water Conveyance Efficiency: Water conveyance efficiency is the ratio between water delivered to the irrigated plot and total quantity delivered from source. It is mathematically expressed as:

$$E_c = \frac{W_f}{W_r} \times 100$$

In irrigation distribution networks i.e., distributaries, water courses, etc., the water conveyance efficiency is used to find out what percentage of the released water at the head gate actually received at the farm and is an index of the seepage losses in the conveyance losses. Thus low water conveyance efficiency implies that much of the water released from the source is lost due to seepage in transit from the source to the field.

2. Water Application Efficiency: The losses during conveyance and due to uneven distribution, evaporation and deep percolation further reduce efficiency of irrigation water. It is the ratio between the quantity of water stored in the root zone and the water delivered to the farm.

$$E_a = \frac{W_s}{W_f} \times 100$$

The concept of water application efficiency is often applied to a project, a farm or a field to estimate the irrigation practices. All the factors, which influence the outline of the surface irrigation system therefore directly, affect the application efficiency. Thus low water application efficiency hinted that much of the applied quantity of water has been lost due to runoff or deep percolation.

3. Water Storage Efficiency: Water storage efficiency is the ratio between water stored in the root zone and water needed in the root zone before irrigation and it is mathematically expressed as:

$$E_s = \frac{W_s}{W_n} \times 100$$

The concept of water storage efficiency is useful in evaluating irrigation methods, especially under limited water supply conditions. It is also crucial when soil with low infiltration rates is to be irrigated. This concept is also useful when the salt balance of the root zone has to be taken into consideration and the leaching requirement needs to be calculated. Low storage efficiency implies that water application is far but actually needed.

4. Water Distribution Efficiency: It is the ratio between the average numerical deviations in the depth of water stored from the average depth stored during irrigation (Y) and the average depth stored during irrigation (d). It is mathematically expressed as:

$$E_d = \left(1 - \frac{Y}{d}\right) \times 100$$

Water distribution within the field is properly measured by water distribution efficiency. Low distribution efficiency means non-uniformity in the irrigation water penetration in the soil because of uneven land levelling. Water for irrigation cannot flow over the soil perfectly. There are low patches where water will penetrate more and there are high patches where water cannot reach. This leaves some places without irrigation unless excess irrigation water is applied. Excess water application lowers irrigation efficiency.

5. Project Efficiency: Project efficiency can be defined as the ratio between the average depth of water stored in the root zone during irrigation and water diverted from the reservoir. It is mathematically expressed as:

$$E_p = \frac{W_s}{W_r} \times 100$$

Farm overall irrigation efficiency is a product of:

$$E_f = E_a \times E_s \times E_d$$

The overall irrigation efficiency for a project is the product of:

$$E_p = E_a \times E_s \times E_d \times E_c$$

Conclusion

With the increased competition for water and therefore the cost of irrigation, irrigation efficiency must be considered when making management decisions. Determination of the needed quantity of irrigation water is estimated by application efficiency. Without realising the actual quantity of water the crop can use, the field could even be over or under irrigated. Various types of irrigation systems requires deep knowledge of the water application efficiencies so that it will help producers make informed decisions about the value and return related to switching from one irrigation system to a different one.

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